

Improving Medical Emergency Team Response Time for Urgent Care Patients in Primary Health Care Centers, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

Background: Emergency healthcare systems are of increasing concern in international healthcare developments and the global fight against the burdens of disease. Concerns about focusing on ambulance response time as a single indicator are addressed by showing a case-sensitive approach for developing emergency health care systems that in return can identify ambulance response as the main indicator for a particular system. **Problem description:** Data collected by monitoring the time of receiving the call at the ambulance division until transport time.

Methods: The fishbone diagram is used as a tool for understanding the process variation, investigate and eliminating unusual occurrences by the following methodology: M.M.M.

Main outcomes: Responding time in emergency cases not exceeding 5 minutes; To improve responding time; To improve types of communication; To improve compliance with the logbook of the emergency referred cases. The intervention plan was Continuous Training for the staff and Clear Guidelines for emergency calls. Review and assess the actual implementation of the project. Data will be collected by an Emergency Medical specialist. A copy of the data should be sent to CQI for a continuous monitoring process. Check the data for process improvement (incident report analysis). Document the results of the change. Modify the change, if necessary and possible. The Emergency Medical Technicians quality coordinator will check the Data. Continue improvement by close monitoring of the compliance.

Results: the mean response time dropped from 15 minutes in January 2023 to less than 5 minutes in December 2023.

Conclusion: this initiative positively impacts the emergency team's response time and improves patient satisfaction. Response time reduction was evident, and the quality of the health care service was improved. Reduction of response time also improved emergency preparedness

Introduction

Emergency healthcare systems are of increasing concern in international healthcare developments and the global fight against the burdens of disease.

Concerns about focusing on ambulance response time as a single indicator are addressed by showing a case-sensitive approach for developing emergency health care systems that in return can identify ambulance response as the main indicator for a particular system.

In 2006 Jeffrey L. Saver, conducted research about time and how important is it MD, TIME IS BRAIN emphasizes that human tissue is rapidly lost so fast intervention is required [1].

In 2008 Elliott M. Antman, MD, FACC the quick approach helped reduce life-threatening in such patients considered TIME IS MUSCLE [2].

In 2011 Paulette Dorney, MSN, RN, CCRN, Chaos or Control, an Educational Initiative, staff development educators play a significant role in the design and

More Information

How to cite this article: Alamri SA, Alanazi AM, Alanazi AA, Alotaibi AF, Maher M, Kofi M. Improving Medical Emergency Team Response Time for Urgent Care Patients in Primary Health Care Centers, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2024;2(5):285-89.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).30

Keywords:

Emergency Medical Technician,
PHC,
Response time.

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implementation of teaching strategies to ensure knowledge and skill acquisition of healthcare providers, teamwork, and competency in CPR [3].

In 2013 Leah A. Scaramuzzo, MSN, RN-BC, AOCN®, Yuk Wong, RN, BSN, MA, OCN®, Kira Lynn Voitle, BSN, RN, OCN®, and Janet Gordils-Perez, MA, ANP-BC, AOCNP Ambulatory and outpatient centers constantly are challenged with administrating cancer treatments in an efficient and safe way [4].

In October 2017 Dr. Mary Bemker, Dr. Nadia Luna, and Dr. Joshua Gadd, conducted a study about how Engaging staff in team-building activities can assist in creating a productive worthy trusted work environment [5].

In 2023 Angela N. Ikeme, DNP(c), MSN, RN, NE-BC did a study about Deteriorating Patients and how Delivering high-quality care depends on good working

relationships, effective teamwork, and the clinical competencies of all team members relative to their professional roles and responsibilities [6]

In 2023 Sadiq Al Salman, and colleagues in a work titled BRIDGE TO BETTER CARE, a considerable proportion of healthcare providers demonstrate a good understanding of TIA definition and management, however, the lack of significant predictors for good knowledge and attitude suggests the need for more comprehensive strategies to enhance TIA management expertise across healthcare professionals [7].

Problem Addressed

- Problem description: Data collected by monitoring the time of receiving the call at the ambulance division until transport time.

Figure 1: Causes for Delays in Response Times of EMT

Methods

The fishbone diagram is used as a tool for understanding the process variation, Investigate and eliminating unusual occurrences by the following methodology: M.M.M

Main outcome: Responding time in emergency cases not exceeding 5 minutes.

To improve responding time.

To improve types of communication.

To improve compliance with the logbook of the emergency referred cases.

The intervention plan was Continuous Training for the staff and Clear Guidelines for emergency calls.

Review and assess the actual implementation of the project.

Data will be collected by Emergency Medical specialist. A copy of the data should be sent to CQI for a continuous monitoring process.

Check the data for process improvement (incident report analysis).

Document the results of the change.

Modify the change, if necessary and possible.

The Emergency Medical Technicians quality coordinator will check the Data.

Continue improvement by close monitoring of the compliance.

Emergency healthcare systems are of increasing concern in international healthcare developments and the global fight against the burdens of disease.

Concerns about focusing on ambulance response time as a single indicator are addressed by showing a case sensitive approach for developing emergency health care systems that in return can identify ambulance response as main indicator for a particular system

Table 1. Organize Team

Position	Department	Roles & Responsibilities
Head of Ambulance division	EMT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supervise and monitor the implementation of the project
Deputy of EMT division	EMT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supervision and monitoring
EMT Quality Coordinator	EMT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leads the team in the implementation
EMT Specialist	EMT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Educate and train all ambulance staff
Supplies coordinator	Supplies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provides needed supplies for the implementation of the project

The fishbone diagram is used as a tool for understanding the process variation, Investigate and eliminating unusual occurrences by the following methodology: M.M.M
Attached fish bone diagram

Main outcome: Responding time in emergency cases not exceeding 5 minutes.
To improve responding time.
To improve types of communication.
To improve compliance with the logbook of the emergency referred cases.

Cause and Effect ("Fishbone") Diagram

Figure 2: Root Cause Analysis for the Delay in EMT Response Times

Table 2: Intervention Activities to Expedite Response Times of EMT

Activity	Responsible	Target Date	Resource	Outcome
Continuous Training to the staff	EMT Quality Coordinator	ASAP	Manpower	ongoing
Clear Guidelines for emergency calls	EMT Specialist	ASAP	Manpower	ongoing

- **Tools:** distribution of activities and responsibilities among the EMT team at PHC.
- Review and assess the actual implementation of the project

- Data will be collected by emt specialist.
- Copy of the data should be sent to CQI for a continuous monitoring process.

- Check the data for process improvement (incident report analysis)
- Document the results of the change.
- Modify the change, if necessary and possible
- The Data will be checked by the emt quality coordinator
- Continue improvement by close monitoring of the compliance

Results

Table 3: Difference in EMT Response Time by Month

	Difference Time	Aim Results
Jan-23	0:15	00:05
Feb-23	00:13	00:05
Mar-23	00:11	00:05
Apr-23	00:10	00:05
May-23	00:08	00:05
Jun-23	00:10	00:05
Jul-23	00:09	00:05
Aug-23	00:07	00:05
Sep-23	00:06	00:05
Oct-23	00:05	00:05
Nov-23	00:04	00:05
Dec-23	00:04	00:05

Figure 3: Improve Responding Time and aim Results for Transfer from PHC to ED - 2023

Conclusion

the study described improvement in response time during 2023, from 15 minutes to under 5 minutes. This reduction in the mean response time dropped from 15 minutes in January 2023 to less than 5 minutes in December 2023, which is a 10-minute difference can be life-saving and impact both patient satisfaction and overall procedures and early intervention. The positive impact of this reduction is observable in patient satisfaction and patient outcomes. This initiative positively impacts the emergency team's response time

and improves patient satisfaction. Response time reduction was evident, and the quality of the health care service was improved. Reduction of response time also improved emergency preparedness

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